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SOCIAL NETWORKING IN STRESS-EXPOSED PLANTS

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Abstract

Throughout the life cycle, plants are exposed to a wide range of environmental factors, some of which may be harmful to their capacity to grow and develop to the fullest extent possible. The ability of a plant to respond rapidly and effectively to stress is one of the most critical aspects in determining its optimal output and survival. Plants have developed a mechanism for communication and signaling throughout their evolutionary history. Plants emit volatile organic compounds (VOCs) into the atmosphere to warn other plants of impending danger. Neighboring plants exposed to volatile organic chemicals develop their own defense systems in response to the stress. The basil plant (*Ocimum basilicum*) has been subjected to three different salinized water treatments (0, 40, and 80 mM NaCl) in order to investigate plant communication under stress. The main volatile organic compounds (VOCs) found in basil leaves were detected using analytical headspace-gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (HS-GC/MS). In basil, six signaling terpenes and one monoterpene were found. Under saline stress, eucalyptol synthesis and emission are intensified. The monoterpenes beta-phellandrene showed a tendency to decline under stress. Interestingly, the concentration of 4-carene is enhanced, while emission of its isomere 3-carene is reduced. In contrast to this, when exposed to stress, the concentrations of pinene, beta-ocimene, and alpha-camphene increased in moderately salinized solutions and decreased in substantially salinized solutions.

Key words: *plants communication, VOC, basil, terpenes, GCMS.*

Introduction

A critical aspect of contemporary agriculture is soil salinization. The production of plants is adversely affected by salinization of agricultural land, which further intensifies soil degradation. Retention of soluble salts in the soil leads to salinization of the soil. It occurs either naturally or as a result of inappropriate human activity, especially farming methods, intense industrialization pressure, and climate changes. In addition to reducing the yield of most crops, salinity affects the physical and chemical characteristics of the soil. There is a noticeable acceleration of the pace of soil salinization. It is anticipated that 50% of agricultural soil will become holomorphic by 2050 (Nachshon, 2018).

During their evolution plants developed a specific mechanism of communication as response to stress. When exposed plants experience stress, stress triggers set off a series of events that include gene expression, signaling cascade reactions, and morphological changes. For stress reactions to be successful or unsuccessful, signal processing time is crucial. Plants can communicate through sophisticated systems of mycorrhizal networks, electrical impulses, and volatile organic molecules released into the atmosphere or soil (Karban, 2008; Sharifi and Ryu, 2021). Volatile organic compounds, or VOCs, emitted by plants exposed to stress, have a particular composition and ratio of compounds. Plants react to messages containing volatile organic compounds (VOCs) by initiating a specific defense mechanism. For instance, the plant may produce specific secondary metabolites to protect itself from a particular kind of stress (Abbas et al., 2021, Rozenkranz et al., 2021).

With nearly sixty varieties, basil is an aromatic member of the *Lamiacea* family. Because of its essential oil concentration and aromatic flavor, basil is utilized extensively in both the culinary and pharmaceutical industry. The predominant aromatic profiles found in each of the species can be used to classify them into chemotypes, plant subspecies that share the same morphological traits but differ in the amounts of chemical compounds they produce in their essential oils (Muráriková et al., 2017). Monoterpenoids, methyleugenol, sesquiterpenoids, and phenylpropanoids fall within this category. Furthermore, there have also been reports of phenolic profiles. The differences in the content of essential oils are caused by factors such as cultivation conditions (temperature, light quality, and quantity), species and cultivar, growth season, leaf position and age, harvesting techniques, and extraction methods (Tangpao et al., 2022). The objective of the present study was to examine the relationship between plant communication and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) emission in limiting settings of saline stress.

Material and methods

The experiment constituted growing plants from seeds in the ecological-climatic conditions of Novi Sad, Serbia (45.2396° N, 19.8227° E). The basil seeds were sown at the beginning of March 2024 into a commercial substrate. When the basil seedling reached 5 cm in plant height, they were transferred to the experimental pots. Without causing any water stress, the seedlings were irrigated by ponding water in each pot until they had grown to an average height of 10-15 cm and had become acclimated to the soil. Following the original harvest of the basil plants in order to establish consistency among the plants, treatments were applied at regular basis. The irrigation interval and saline solution concentration were set at three days and 0, 40, and 80 mM, respectively. After 30 days of exposure to saline stress, basil leaves were harvested and analyzed for qualitative and descriptive composition of VOCs.

Basil varieties grown under stress and under control were analyzed for volatile chemicals using gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC/MS, 7890A/ 7694E, Agilent Technologies, USA), in scan mode. The instrument used a 30-m Agilent J&W DB-5MS Ultra Inert column (0.25 mm × 0.25 μm film thickness). For GCMS headspace analysis was used 0.3g of basil samples.

Results and Discussion

In terms of descriptive results, a total of six signaling VOCs were identified in this study (table 1), among which carene exists in isomer forms of 4- and 3-carene. Detailed analysis of the complete volatile compounds profile confirmed that terpenes are essential for stress-related communication. This finding is in line with recent studies. Namely, a thorough examination of the entire profile of volatile molecules highlighted terpenes and terpenoids, the most diverse class of plant secondary metabolites, as critical for stress-related communication (Rozenkranz et al., 2021). Terpenes, which include isoprene, monoterpenes, and sesquiterpenes, make up the greatest group of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) generated by plants under suboptimal growing conditions. Terpenes have the potential to serve as a chemical language for plant communication. Different classes of terpenes are used for warning under specific stress. While in plant-insect interactions, mono- and sesquiterpenes act as communication molecules, isoprene, the smallest and most often released terpene, has a role in abiotic stress resistance (Karban, 2008; Boncan et al., 2021, Abbas et al., 2022;).

In comparison to control plants, there was an increase in the levels of total eucalyptol and 4-carene following exposure to moderate and severe (40 mM and 80 mM NaCl treatment, respectively) saline stress. Specifically, under mild saline stress, the ratio of the cyclic monoterpenoid eucalyptol is raised by 60%. After further exposure to higher concentration of

NaCl, the initial rise declined, however, it remained higher than in the group of reference plants (Table 1). Full gas-mass chromatogram was shown in figure 1.

Table 1. Signaling terpenes emitted by basil leaves exposed to saline stress

Terpene	Ratio T1*/C**	Ratio T2***/C**
Pinene	1.18	0.87
Alpha-camphene	1.19	0.88
Beta-phellandrene	0.90	0.76
Eucalyptol	1.60	1.29
Beta-ocimene	1.11	0.81
Gamma-terpinene	1.41	0.76
4-carene	1.13	1.09
3-carene	0.95	0.58

*T1: treatment of mild salinization of 40mM NaCl solution

**C: control group

***T2: treatment of severe salinization of 80mM NaCl solution

Bicyclic monoterpenes 4-carene showed a similar pattern, with concentrations rising by 13% and 9% under moderate and severe salt stress, respectively. However, during salinization, the levels of the monoterpenes beta-phellandrene and 3-carene decreased in a corresponding manner in comparison to plants cultivated under optimal conditions and not exposed to stress (0.90 and 0.76 and 0.95 and 0.58, respectively, figure 1).

Fig.1 Full GCMS chromatogram in scan mode with mass spectra for a) Eucalyptol and b) 3-Carene

In contrast, the salinization caused decrease of monoterpene beta-phellandrene and 3-carene levels (0.90 and 0.76 and 0.95 and 0.58 compared to plants grown under optimal conditions respectively). Alpha-camphene, beta-ocimene, and pinene release are intensified under mild stress circumstances, however their production is suppressed at 80 mM NaCl concentration.

Compared to abiotic factors, effects of biotic-induced plant-to-plant communication have been studied far more. While the emission of volatile monoterpenoids is triggered by all types of stress, the production of aromatic volatiles appears to be promoted mostly by insect attack. Additionally, in line with our findings, the volatile monoterpenes, such as pinenes and ocimene, are activated by both biotic and abiotic stress (Abbas et al., 2022; Rosenkranz et al., 2021). Moreover, alpha-camphene may serve as a marker for biochemical alterations occurring at infection, whereas pinene, linalool, and ocimene are induced by biotic and abiotic stress (Arimura et al., 2011; Lee et al., 2014, Kleiber et al., 2017, Boncan et al., 2021).

Similar to our findings, several studies have linked the variation in 3-carene concentration to the plant's response to abiotic stress (Lee et al., 2014; Kleiber et al., 2017). Our findings are consistent with Lee et al. (2014), who found terpenine emission in rice under abiotic stress. According to Zebelo et al. (2012) and Kleiber et al. (2017), exposure to biotic and abiotic stress has been shown to cause the emission of gamma-phellandrene in the atmosphere.

Until now, research has not determined a change in beta-ocimene synthesis due to exposure to abiotic factors, but only due to insect invasion (Arimura et al., 2011, Lee et al., 2014). This finding gives room for beta-ocimene to be considered as a candidate for VOCs involved in communication in stressful circumstances, particularly in salinity-related situations.

The alternations in beta-phellandrene synthesis noticed between control and stressed plants can be explained with prior outcomes at gene expression level. Conditions of drought or excessive salinity alter the volatile emission in plants (Fernández-Martínez et al., 2018, Penuelas et al., 2005). A study that cross-referenced the volatile ingredients indicated many alterations in gene expression under constant salt stress. The plant can be protected from abiotic stresses by changes in VOC composition, such as the production of monoterpenes and isoprene. Most of the genes involved in volatile emission were suppressed in tomatoes exposed to salt (Benjamin et al., 2012) and beta-phellandrene synthase was one of these.

Our results demonstrate that concentrations of alpha-camphene, beta-ocimene, and pinene increase after initial exposure to moderate saline stress. Continued exposure to high salt concentrations causes a drop in their levels. This can be explained by the fact that increased salt concentrations are toxic to plants and that metabolic activities of stressed plants are reduced to minimum (Xu and Wu, 2021).

Conclusions

Detailed study of the entire profile of volatile chemicals verified that terpenes are necessary for communication linked to saline stress. For warning under particular stress conditions, different classes of terpenes and their mode/level of synthesis are employed. Upon exposure to moderate and severe salinity stress, there were variations in the amounts of six signaling volatile chemicals compared to control plants. These compounds include alpha-camphene, beta-ocimene, carene (which represents 4-carene 3-carene in two isomer forms), eucalyptol, and beta-phellandrene. The novel aspect is that, up until now, studies have only found that insect invasion causes changes in beta-ocimene production. This result allows beta-ocimene to be taken into consideration as a potential volatile organic compound (VOCs) implicated in stressful situations, especially those including salt. Our findings indicate that following an initial exposure to moderate saline stress, concentrations of alpha-camphene, beta-ocimene, and pinene rise. Their levels decrease with continued exposure to high salt concentrations. This makes sense given that plants are poisonous to higher salt concentrations and that stressed plants have minimal metabolic activity. As a result of initial exposure to moderate saline stress, our data show that concentrations of alpha-camphene, beta-ocimene, and pinene rise. They decrease as a result of prolonged exposure to high salt concentrations. This implies

that stressed plants exhibit minimal metabolic activity and higher salt concentrations are toxic to plants.

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